

HISTORY OF THE STUDY OF ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD
BABUR'S WORK "MUBAYIN"

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Annotation In this article, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's work Mubayyin is analyzed and the history of its study from the scholar's point of view is revealed, as well as the essence of this work is also revealed.

Key words: Mubayyin, religious work, political and scientific spheres, Masnavi genre, religious science, jurisprudence, poem.

"Today, when our dear Motherland is entering a new stage of national development - the Third Renaissance period, fundamental changes are taking place in all aspects of our life, the in-depth study and popularization of Babur Mirza's priceless heritage is becoming more important."

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

Studying the manuscripts that embody the life experiences, religious, secular, legal and political views of our great-great-grandfathers over the centuries is considered one of the urgent tasks of today. The head of our state paid special attention to the preservation of our historical and cultural wealth, its scientific research, in particular, to the study of the legacy of the great poet and statesman Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. In our republic, research is being carried out in various directions related to the life of Babur Mirzo and Babur studies. A number of works have been carried out in our country to study Babur's life and work and restore his legacy to the world. In particular, the research of the International "Babur" Public Foundation is commendable. As a result of the research carried out by the members of the expedition over the years, the Museum "Babur and World

Culture" was established in Andijan. The publication of important works called "Babur Encyclopaedia", "Babur Kulliyati", and the establishment of the magazine "Babur and the World" were recognized as a great event in our cultural life.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is one of our great compatriots who took an important place in the social, political and scientific spheres of world history. In addition to being the ruler who founded the "Great Babur Empire" in India at the beginning of the 16th century, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is also a jurist who left behind a rich legal legacy. In the study of Babur's rich heritage, the fact that he was a multifaceted statesman and thinker is of great importance. We can see that in Babur's works, along with dozens of disciplines such as literature, art, geography, history, music, local history, ethnography, mineralogy, ideas related to politics and law also have a significant place. possible The study of Babur's main scientific and spiritual heritage, in particular, his political and legal views, does not lose its importance.

Babur wrote "Mubayyin" during his campaigns to India in 1521. Written in the style of Masnavi, this work is devoted to Islamic jurisprudence and Sharia beliefs and contains interesting information about Mowarounnahr and the socio-economic life of that time in India. In the "Mubayyin", which was intended as a program for Crown Prince Humayun and Kamran Mirza, at the same time, Shari'a standards were also stated about prayer, zakat and pilgrimage. During these years, Babur completed his scientific treatise on one of the main issues of Eastern poetry, aruz weight, its theory and practice.

"Mubayyin" is a philosophical-religious work, in which Babur Mirza explained how the five pillars of Islam should be correctly performed within the framework of the Hanafi school of thought.

This work consists of five books:¹

1) Book of Faith;

¹ <https://sammuslim.uz/oz/press/news/mubayyan-va-nasriy-bayoni-bobur-mirzo-buyuk-faqih-birinchi-mavzu?print=on>

- 2) Prayer book;
- 3) Book of Zakat;
- 4) Fasting book;
- 5) Book of Hajj.

The manuscript was copied in one of the most beautiful lines of calligraphy in the old Uzbek language - nastaliq letter. It has also been translated into Persian.

According to information, this manuscript was written down in India 400 years ago. A copy of the "Mubayyin" manuscript was brought to Iran through Kashmir. The book has been kept in the collection of the "Guliston" palace museum for more than 120 years.

It should be noted that the work "Mubayyin" was included in the list of foreign manuscripts related to Uzbekistan by the Center for the Study of Cultural Assets of the Republic of Uzbekistan under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

A copy of the book was presented to the Uzbek diplomats by Mohammad Reza Nassiri, the deputy chairman of the Academy of Persian Language and Literature of Iran. This manuscript is written in the old Uzbek language, and it is significant that the Persian translation of the text is given under each line. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's work "Mubayyin" is written in the Masnavi style, dedicated to Islamic jurisprudence and Sharia beliefs, and contains interesting information on the socio-economic life of Movaroonnahr and India at that time.

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The presence of "Mubayyin" manuscripts in various manuscript funds of the world indicates that this work is extremely important for all times. However, because manuscripts were time-consuming and expensive to produce, these works were usually kept as rare works in private libraries and treasuries, with limited access to the literate public.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, as a result of the efforts of our country's enlighteners, one after another lithographs (lithographs) began to be opened in the city of Tashkent, and an opportunity arose to convey the rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors to the general public. The fact that Baburmirza's "Mubayyin" was included among the books presented to the general public for the first time during this period is a clear proof of how great the value of this source was for our people and, most importantly, that it was paid attention to and demanded.

This edition was published by the enlightened publisher Mulla Mir Makhdum ibn Shah Yunus Tashkandi in 1905 in the city of Tashkent in the lithography of O. Porsef. The first descriptive information about this lithographic publication was published in the press in 2008 by Jaloliddin Jorayev, a source scientist, doctor of philology.

The great historian and scientist Abdulhai Lakhnavi-Hasani writes in *Nuzhat ul-Khavatir* "A Walk of Memories": "He was named Zahiriddin Muhammad by Hazrat Khoja Ubaidullah Ahror, but he was known as Baburshah among the Turkic peoples. He is as knowledgeable as the sea in many sciences. His jurisprudence in Hanafi (based on the Hanafi school) is a work called "Mubayyan", to which Sheikh Zainuddin (ibn Qutbuddin al-Hanafi) al-Khawafi wrote a commentary called "Mubayyin" ("*Nuzhat ul-khawatir*" - "Walk of Memories", Page 314.) Accordingly, it is clear that the title of the work is "Mubayyan".

Hasankhoja Nisari's work "Muzakkiri ahbob" ("Memoir of the Beloved"), one of the 16th-century tazkiras, says: "Babur king's virtues are numerous and his perfections are countless. His treatise on Aruz ("*Risalai Aruz*") is a sea full of jewels and charms. He explained the issues of jurisprudence in another treatise, which is a sign of the wisdom of the writer. He has good poems in Turkish and Persian. The name of Oshal fiqh treatise is "Mubayyan" (translated from Persian by Ismail Bekjon. Tashkent, People's Heritage Publishing House named after Abdulla Qadiri, 1993. pp. 51-53).

Academician Sabohat Azimjonova, who studied and analyzed Babur's work *Mubayyin* twenty years ago, gave many positive descriptions about this work. According to experts, Babur Mirza's socio-philosophical and religious-legal views were part of the complex of views of Islamic jurists of the Abu Hanifa school. That is why, through the reading of many masterpieces, such as those listed above, he mastered the socio-philosophical and aesthetic content of the thinking of the past and his time. Our great ancestor not only deeply mastered these works, but as a mature scientist, he developed the level of thinking of the time in which he lived to another level.

"*Mubayyin*" is written in the *Masnavi* genre, and jurisprudential issues are explained with deep knowledge through the unique narrative style of Babur, a scholar, writer and king. In order to slowly and firmly inculcate the fundamentals of Islam in the reader's mind, the artful use of artistic means is worthy of praise.

All this, in turn, serves as a basis for the scientific study of Babur Mirza's religious views and his contribution to religious sciences as a jurist. During the years of independence, Babur Mirza's work "*Mubayyin*" was published three times in our country. The first edition was published in "MUMTOZ CO'Z" publishing house in 2011, the second one in 2000 in Abdulla Qadiri publishing house, and the third edition in 2020 in "Sharq" publishing house.

The fact that the work "*Mubayyin*" written by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is being perfected from edition to edition is worthy of all attention and respect. Therefore, a deep respect for one's history, accumulated experience, and intellectual potential, which is considered the greatest wealth in the world, is the basis of the material and spiritual development of any country.

It should be said that the third edition of this book was created by the well-known poet, translator and scholar Mirzo Kenjabek. "*Mubayyin*", on the one hand, belongs to the series of remarkable works created in the Uzbek language and belongs to the pen of a classical poet, and on the other hand, it is a bright example of religious and literary literature that fully reflects the richness and richness of our

language. This work is a valuable resource for researchers in various fields such as Islamic scholars and jurists, historians and philosophers, linguists and literary scholars.

When the time comes, it should be noted that great attention is being paid to the research of Babur Mirzo's life and scientific and creative activities, not only in Uzbekistan, but on a global scale. In the East - Sheikh Zain, Mulla Mir Makhdum Toshkandi, S.Azimjonova, S.Shukrullaeva, O.Husanboev, N.Rasulzoda, Ye.Berezin, A.Samoylovich. It is appropriate to mention the services of scientists and publishers such as Fuod Koprulu, Tanju Oral Seyhan, as well as Indian scientists Abul Fazl Allomiy and Badouni, and orientalists such as Bevirij and Springer in the West.²

In conclusion, every good deed done to study the works of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, every book published in this regard is a new path opened for deeper knowledge and understanding of Babur's personality, life and work.

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